

1 Article

2 Impact of FO Operating Pressure on Deformation, 3 Efficiency and Concentration Polarisation with Novel 4 Links to CFD

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13 Abstract: Forward Osmosis (FO) modules currently suffer from performance efficiency limitations
14 due to concentration polarisation (CP), as well as pressure drops during operation. There is
15 incentive to further reduce CP effects, as well as optimise spacer design for pressure drop
16 improvements and mechanical support. In this study, the effects of applying transmembrane
17 pressure (TMP) on FO membrane deformation and the subsequent impact on module performance
18 was investigated by comparing experimental data to 3D computational fluid dynamics (CFD)
19 simulations for three commercial FO modules. At a TMP of 1.5 bar the occlusion of the draw-channel
20 induced by longitudinal pressure hydraulic drop was comparable for the Toray (16%) and HTI
21 modules (12%), however, the hydraulic perimeter of the Profiera module was reduced by 46%. CFD
22 simulation of the occluded channels indicated that change in hydraulic perimeter due to a 62%
23 increase in shear strain resulted in a 31% increase in Reynolds Number. This reduction in channel
24 dimensions enhanced osmotic efficiency by reducing CP via improved draw-channel
25 hydrodynamics which significantly disrupted the ECP (External concentration polarisation) layer.
26 Furthermore, simulations indicated that Reynolds number experienced only modest increases with
27 applied TMP and that shear strain at the membrane surface was found the most important factor
28 when predicting flux performance enhancement which varied between the different modules. This
29 work suggests that a numerical approach to assess the effects of draw-spacers on pressure drop and
30 CP can optimize and reduce investment in design and validation of FO module designs.

31 **Keywords:** Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), spacers, Draw Channel Contraction, Pressure
32 Assisted Osmosis, Concentration Polarisation (CP)

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34 1. Introduction

35 An increasing global demand for potable water, as well as efficient treatment of wastewater, has
36 driven research into forward osmosis (FO) as an alternative to current processes [1]. FO provides
37 benefits when compared to other pressure-only driven processes, such as lower hydraulic pressure
38 and lower fouling operation [2]. FO processes have been investigated widely across a range of
39 applications and modes of operation, with pressure-assisted osmosis (PAO) and FO-reverse osmosis
40 (FO-RO) hybrids evaluated in potential options [3-7]. However, concentration polarisation (CP),
41 reverse solute diffusion (RSD) and pressure considerations within the module currently hinder
42 greater industrial interest in the process [1, 7].

43 CP is a phenomenon affecting membrane processes whereby a solute gradient forms close to the
44 surface of, or within a membrane that hinders flux performance. External concentration polarisation

(ECP) is found in all membrane processes and is a buildup of solute within the boundary layer of the membrane surface, which lowers flux performance and hinders the concentration gradient that drives FO processes. Internal concentration polarisation (ICP) is a concentration gradient within the membrane support layer, that is specific to FO processes. The ICP gradient occurs within the support structure of the membrane that, in turn, acts against the osmotic gradient which drives FO processes [1, 8, 9]. ICP is an inherent problem with the structure of the membrane and is reported to be unmitigated with an optimisation of operating conditions alone [8]. Additionally, ICP is reported as the main CP factor impacting flux performance in FO processes when compared to ECP, especially when the membrane active-layer is faces the feed-side [10, 11]. To assess the impact of CP on FO processes, numerical models have been developed to account for ICP and ECP's effect on flux [8, 10]. These CP models were developed by a modulus approach, whereby depending on the membrane orientation, a moduli was determined for ICP and ECP (either dilutive or concentrative) [6, 8, 10-12]. The CP moduli are typically considered in pairs and during module operation in active-layer feed side (AL-FS) mode, there is considered to be concentrative ECP on the feed-side and dilutive ICP on the draw-side (and vice-versa). Novel flux models that account for wide-ranging temperatures or the diffusivity of draw solutes have since been developed to predict performance for a wider range of operating conditions [11, 12]. Additionally, novel models that consider ECP on both the the draw-side and feed-side of FO membranes have been developed. However, the channel hydrodynamics must be accurately known and this dual layer ECP approach has only been considered under perfectly rectangular channel conditions, only accounting for spacer effects on mass transfer with considerable simplification [13-15]. Current approaches assume a Reynolds number based on overall channel flow, set this value and subsequently compare hydrodynamic outputs such as pressure and velocity profiles [15, 16]. The use of CFD analysis to assist the calculation of a Reynolds number in a spacer-filled channel has not yet been applied to the calculation of mass transfer coefficients in CP modelling.

Pressure considerations within FO processes are an emerging area of research, in both PAO and the minor amount of pressure typically required to circulate draw and feed solutions. While PAO is the use of FO with applied pressure assisting flux performance, even within regular FO processes it has been that 0.5bar of pressure is needed to circulate fluid in 8-inch FO modules [17]. The resultant transmembrane pressure (TMP) has been found to cause deformation of the membrane into the draw-channel, resulting in the draw-channel contraction recently studied in the literature [18-21]. Furthermore, the applied TMP has been observed to cause a long term compaction of the membrane after operation with moderate (1-2.5bar) pressure [3]. The transport properties of FO membranes under applied pressure has recently been explored, finding no significant changes until the active layer is compromised [22]. However, the effects of mechanical strain on flow profiles and CP has not been well established in the literature. Membrane processes usually require a spacer to provide mechanical support and the separation between membrane channels in a module [23]. This has led to spacer designs that offer low mechanical support as a tradeoff for unimpeded fluid flow, and hence a lower pressure drop [17, 18, 21]. While the impact of draw-spacer contraction has been reported on pressure drops and fouling potential, the effects studied have been on the relative contribution of deformation against CP effects [19].

CFD has been utilised as a means of exploring detailed hydrodynamic assessments in FO processes [18, 24]. CFD can provide information not experimentally available of membrane modules, such a turbulence analysis through Reynolds number distributions, velocity profiles as well as shear strain analysis [25, 26]. Shear strain has a known relationship to fouling and ECP mitigation in membrane processes, leading to its use in the literature to inform spacer and module design predictions[27-29]. Additionally, shear strain has been reported to significantly impact flux improvements in FO processes [30]. However, the limitations on how the relative importance of Reynolds number and shear strain analysis are still needed to further optimise how effectively CFD analysis can enhance spacer design.

This paper aims to firstly assess the degree of deformation under applied TMP within commercially available FO membrane modules. Secondly, to provide a detailed hydrodynamic

97 assessment on the effects of TMP on the draw-channel of commercial FO modules using CFD.
98 Lastly, this paper aims to numerically assess the efficiency and CP in the modules and subsequent
99 effects under applied TMP, hence establish a quantified relationship between TMP and CP. The link
100 between a CFD assessment, deformation and CP aims to provide a means by which improvements
101 can be predicted and assessed without the need for costly production and experimental testing of
102 spacer designs across FO modules.

103 2. Materials and Methods

104 2.1 CFD Modelling of membrane processes

105 3D CFD models were developed for 3 commercially available FO modules, 2 SW modules (a
106 CTA from HTI and TFC from Toray) as well as a PF module from Porifera). CFD modelling of three
107 FO module processes was based on the method initially developed in [21], with modifications for
108 further geometry and design parameters of the draw-channel. All 3D CFD simulations were
109 performed using ©Ansys Fluent v19.1. Tetra mesh was employed for each fluid domain, with an
110 average size of 0.2mm. The domain of the spiral-wound (SW) draw-channel has dimensions of
111 1x1.5m for the 8inch modules; shown in Figure 1a, with the mesh outlined in Figure 1c. However,
112 owing to file size limitations in Ansys, only a portion of the PF draw-channel was represented as a
113 segment of the total channel (120x40mm) for the plate-and-frame (PF) module (Figure 1b) with
114 inflation layers of the mesh around the spacers shown in Figure 1d.

115 A no-slip wall condition was utilised to estimate the continuous flow between fluid and spacer,
116 and the two sides of the membrane will be considered symmetrical for the purpose of simplification.
117 All simulations were run using the Semi-Implicit Method for Pressure Linked Equations (SIMPLE)
118 algorithm for pressure-velocity coupling and First Order Upwind (FOU) algorithm for the
119 discretisation of the conservation equations. The PF draw channel was simulated in ANSYS as a
120 single segment, as the flow profile does not change across the module with respect to width, and
121 pressure drop is linear [21].
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Figure 1 3D domains for CFD geometry of FO modules (a) SW geometry (b) PF geometry (c) SW mesh (d) PF mesh.

129 2.2 CP analysis through efficiency and modulus characterisation

130 The experimental data presented in this study is extracted from previous studies, whereby the
 131 membrane active-layer faced the feed-side (for desalination and high fouling solutions) [3, 17, 21].
 132 Additionally, most literature CP models typically agree that dilutive ICP occurs within the support
 133 structure of the membrane on the draw-side, and ECP occurs in the boundary layer on the feed-side
 134 [6, 10-12, 19]. As the feed solution used is deionised water, ECP in the feed can be neglected (i.e. no
 135 solute in the feed). ECP in the draw is characterised using a modulus approach from the literature
 136 that applied the same principles as the feed-side modulus [13]. This paper uses the CP modulus as
 137 presented in most CP studies, all experiments were performed at room temperature and with Red
 138 Sea-salt (RSS) (35.5g/L). Current literature models explore ECP using draw channel hydrodynamics
 139 such as Reynolds number, which assume simple channel geometry (ignoring membrane
 140 deformation) and the effects of spacers. The ECP Reynolds number in this study was calculated using
 141 the CFD and deformation data presented in Sections 3.1-3.3 unless stated otherwise to provide a novel
 142 CFD assisted CP model. While the full CP calculation methods can be found in the literature, a
 143 summary of the exact equations used is given below.

144 Starting with the basic equation for flux in an osmotically driven process, where the effects of
 145 CP are ignored and only osmotic and hydraulic pressures are taken into consideration, as shown in
 146 Equation 1.

$$J_w = A(\pi_{D,b} - \pi_{F,b} + P_{feed} - P_{draw}) \quad (1)$$

147
 148 Where P_{feed} and P_{draw} are the hydraulic pressures of the feed and draw respectively, J_w is
 149 flux, A is the pure water permeability co-efficient, $\pi_{D,b}$ is the osmotic pressure of the draw solution
 150 and $\pi_{F,b}$ is the osmotic pressure of the feed solution.

151 The overall flux efficiency (E) was determined as a measure of the flux when compared the
 152 maximum achievable under a specific hydraulic and osmotic driving force. The OE was determined
 153 to characterize an overall efficiency baseline of a membrane process and can be calculated as the
 154 experimental flux obtained, as a percentage of the maximum achievable flux from Equation 2.
 155

$$E = \frac{J_{w,experimental}}{A(\pi_{D,b} - \pi_{F,b} + P_{feed} - P_{draw})} \quad (2)$$

156
 157 The osmotic efficiency (OE) was determined as a measure of the effectiveness of the osmotic
 158 component of the driving force in Equation 1, and is determined by assuming the hydraulic driving
 159 force is negligibly losing efficiency to CP in a deionized water feed solution (i.e. no feed-side solute).
 160 The osmotic efficiency is extracted from Equation 2, and is shown in Equation 3.
 161

$$OE = \frac{J_{w,experimental}}{A(\pi_{D,b} - \pi_{F,b})} - \frac{(P_{feed} - P_{draw})}{(\pi_{D,b} - \pi_{F,b})} \quad (3)$$

162
 163 The solute resistivity to the membrane 'K', which is a measure of ICP in the support layer to be
 164 used in the final flux equation. K is calculated experimentally, shown in Equation 4:

$$K = \frac{S}{D} = \frac{t\tau}{D\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

165 Where S is the structural parameter of the membrane, D is the solute diffusion co-efficient, t is the
 166 tortuosity, ε is the thickness, and τ is the porosity. The S parameters used in this study were drawn
 167 from the literature and assumed to remain constant.

168 The experimental determination of K is assessed using the experimental flux, fitted to Equation
 169 5.

$$K = \frac{1}{J_w} \ln\left(\frac{A\pi_{D,b} + B}{B + J_w + A\pi_{F,b}}\right) \quad (5)$$

170 Where B is the solute permeability, and K is determined as an average across the experimental range
171 tested.

172 The ICP modulus can then be calculated, as a ratio of the osmotic pressure gradient within the
173 membrane itself, shown in Equation 6.

$$\frac{\pi_{D,m,i}}{\pi_{D,m}} = e^{-J_w K} \quad (6)$$

174 Where $\pi_{m,i}$ is the osmotic pressure of the support layer against the active layer, $\pi_{D,m}$ is the actual
175 osmotic pressure on the membrane surface.

176
177 The effects of ECP are first characterised using the mass transfer coefficient k , based on the CFD
178 hydrodynamic outputs as the channel shape is irregular shown in Equation 7.

$$k = \frac{ShD}{d_h} \quad (7)$$

179
180 Where Sh is the Sherwood number, D is the solute diffusion coefficient and d_h is the hydraulic
181 diameter. It should be noted the Sherwood number is calculated from the fitting parameters for FO
182 [11]. The ECP modulus for the draw-side is then calculated as shown in Equation 8.

$$\frac{\pi_{D,m}}{\pi_{D,b}} = e^{-J_w/k} \quad (8)$$

183 Where $e^{-\frac{J_w}{k}}$ is the ECP modulus on the draw-side.

184 2.3 CFD hydrodynamic parameter analysis

185 CFD analysis provides a detailed analysis including shear strain and Reynolds number, each
186 known to impact membrane performance. The shear strain rate exerted by the fluid on the draw-
187 channel is a measure of the perpendicular force acting on the channel and membrane surface. Shear
188 strain rate is a typically reported CFD output of membrane process modelling as it provides the strain
189 rate of membrane processes with a high degree of accuracy [24, 31]. Wall shear rate increases are
190 associated with improved CP and fouling mitigation. ANSYS Fluent v.19.1 was used to generate shear
191 rate contours of the membrane surface in the draw channels of FO modules, as well as generate
192 average membrane surface and bulk values. This analysis was used to link CFD hydrodynamic
193 parameters with channel occlusion and CP. Shear rate was calculated based on the method presented
194 in previous literature [18], however, a summary of the method is given in Equation 9.

$$Shear\ Rate = \left[2 \frac{\delta U_i}{\delta X_i} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

195 Where U_i is velocity and X_i is the spatial coordinate.

196
197 Reynolds number was characterised to assess the degree of turbulence and mixing in the channel
198 and has been reported in the CFD assessment in narrow spacer filled channels. Reynolds number is
199 used as a channel average in CP models [10], due to links with improved CP and fouling performance
200 in membrane processes [32]. Reynolds number was calculated as both a contour map on the
201 membrane surface as well as average values for the bulk fluid and membrane surface. As with the
202 shear rate analysis, Reynolds number was assessed to establish a relationship between TMP and CP
203 through a hydrodynamic CFD analysis. The method is based on previous literature [18], however, a
204 summary of the factors is given in Equation 10.

$$Re = \frac{\rho_c v_c d_c}{\mu} \tag{10}$$

205 Where ρ is the fluid density, d is mesh cell volume^{1/3}, v_c is velocity magnitude in the cell
 206 and μ is the fluid viscosity. It should be noted the difference between a CFD cell-volume based value
 207 and the value given in ECP models, based on hydraulic diameter (Equation 11).

$$Re_d = \frac{\rho_d v_d d_h}{\mu_d} \tag{11}$$

208 Where Re_d is an overall Reynolds number for the entire draw channel, d_h is the hydraulic
 209 diameter, typically expressed as a rectangle in FO processes ($\frac{2WH}{W+H}$) and the rest of the parameters are
 210 all expressed as channel averages (where W and H are the width and height of the channel
 211 respectively).

212 3. Results and discussion

213 3.1 CFD model validation and membrane deformation analysis

214 TMP in FO processes has been shown to cause draw-channel occlusion, whereby the membrane
 215 deforms into the draw channel [18, 19, 21]. To determine the exact level of occlusion experienced in
 216 a range of FO modules under pressure, models were developed using experimental data at 0 bar and
 217 1.5bar of TMP. Firstly, draw-channels were modelled as 3D CFD geometries and validated against a
 218 range of experimental data reported previously in the literature to assess the degree of membrane
 219 deformation across module and membrane types [17, 21]. The PF (Porifera) module was validated
 220 from previous experimental data, using the method from our previous work [18]. However, a novel
 221 3D geometry for a channel occlusion of 49% was developed to determine the membrane deformation
 222 at 1.5bar of TMP, to establish a comparison point between the 3 commercially available FO modules.
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 225 **Figure. 2** Porifera PF draw-channel CFD validation of draw channel pressure drop against draw
 226 inlet pressure, showing draw channel contraction, validated against experimental data previously
 227 reported [17].

228 The Porifera module (Figure 2) shows pressure-drop behavior following the 0% channel at
 229 lower TMPs (between 0-0.5bar), and with increasing pressure, the pressure drops shift to match the
 230 behavior of the 49% channel, between TMPs of 0.8-1.5bar. The 49% channel occlusion is high when
 231 compared to the relatively low TMP applied, and is due to the lack of mechanical support from the
 232 dot-spacer type used in the module.

233 The SW modules were simulated as 3D geometries of a single sheet, using a pressure-drop
 234 comparison method previously established in the literature [21]. The SW modules were both

235 modelled from a different data-set to the PF module, where the only the TMP was varied (and not
 236 the inlet pressure). This resulted in the 'calibration' approach whereby after the 3D dimensions were
 237 established, the open channel porosity was calibrated the pressure drop at 0bar TMP and the channel
 238 height was varied until the pressure drop matched at 1.5bar TMP.
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241 **Figure 3** Toray SW draw-channel CFD validation of draw channel pressure drop against inlet
 242 pressure, showing draw channel contraction, validated against experimental data previously
 243 reported [21].

244 The Toray 0% occlusion channel (Figure 3) was calibrated against the experimental channel at
 245 negligible TMP. At 1.5bar of TMP, the channel height was contracted such that the experimental
 246 pressure drop matches a channel that is occluded, at 16%. The lower degree of occlusion shown in
 247 the Toray module when compared to the Porifera module (Figure 2) is due to the increase mechanical
 248 support of a fine mesh draw-spacer.
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251 **Figure 4** HTI SW draw-channel CFD validation of draw channel pressure drop against inlet
 252 pressure, showing draw channel contraction validated against experimental data previously
 253 reported [17].

254 The CFD validation of the HTI module (Figure 4) was from the same data-set as the Toray
 255 module, and as such follows the same format. The CFD open channel (0%) was calibrated against the
 256 experimental data at negligible TMP and demonstrates a similar pressure drop to the other SW
 257 module (Toray, Figure 3). At 1.5bar of TMP, the experimental pressure drop matches a CFD geometry
 258 of 12% occlusion. The HTI spacer is a dense/rigid Tricot spacer, with the highest degree of mechanical
 259 support provided across the three modules [17]. The mechanical support of the dense HTI draw
 260 spacer allows for the least deformation, and therefore least channel occlusion (12% at 1.5bar TMP).
 261 Furthermore, the Porifera 'dot-spacer' design for the draw-channel offers by contrast the least
 262 mechanical support [18], and subsequently highest 49% channel occlusion under pressure. Overall,
 263 the three FO modules clearly demonstrate a region of deformation, whereby the pressure-drop
 264 change with inlet pressure is high, physically representing the membrane moving closer to the draw-
 265 channel spacer for mechanical support. Subsequently (but not shown with the reported TMP range
 266 in this study), the pressure-drop gradient is lower, while some further membrane deformation may
 267 occur, the increase in occlusion at higher TMP is significantly slower and expected to reach
 268 insignificance since the membrane rests fully against the spacer or channel wall. From these results,
 269 a comparison point at 1.5bar TMP is now used for the rest of the paper to investigate the effects of
 270 TMP on hydrodynamics, CP, and therefore overall flux performance.

271 3.2 Shear strain analysis

272 Utilising the two comparison points of channel/membrane behaviour at 0 and 1.5bar of TMP, the
 273 effects of TMP on draw channel hydrodynamics can be assessed in detail by 3D CFD simulations run
 274 in ANSYS FLUENT v.19.1. Shear strain analysis is an assessment of the force exerted by a fluid on
 275 the membrane surface, previously reported in the literature for its effects on fouling and more
 276 importantly, ECP [18, 27, 28]. The effects of TMP on the shear rate at the membrane surface, as well
 277 as the bulk fluid, are further investigated and linked with CP considerations directly in later sections
 278 of this study.

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282 **Figure 5** Effect of TMP increase on shear strain rate at the membrane surface, with the right and left
 283 simulations 1 and 1.5bar TMP respectively for (a) Toray (b) HTI (c) Porifera.

284 The Toray module (Figure 5a) shows the most significant change of the SW modules to shear
 285 rate on the membrane surface under the effects of 1.5bar TMP. The membrane shear strain rate
 286 distribution at 0% occlusion shows high shear stress ($657 \pm 63 \text{ s}^{-1}$) within the straight channel of the
 287 membrane leaves, and dead-zones of lower shear rate as expected in the corners ($13 \pm 25 \text{ s}^{-1}$). At 16%
 288 (1.5bar TMP) occlusion, the straight channels that cover the majority of the shear distribution
 289 demonstrate a shear rate increase to $825 \pm 63 \text{ s}^{-1}$, as expected of a narrower channel where the fluid
 290 local cross flow velocity (CFV) increases in proportion to a lower cross-sectional area. The HTI
 291 demonstrates a more uneven distribution of shear strain on the membrane surface (Figure 5c). This
 292 uneven shear strain distribution is likely due to the denser spacer, creating more flow resistance and
 293 higher gradients of strain. Additionally, the initial shear stress is lower ($375 \pm 63 \text{ s}^{-1}$), and explanation
 294 for this can also be found by noting the membrane spacer density, as all simulations were run at the
 295 same CFV (0.1m/s) [17]. The shear strain increase with a 1.5bar TMP of an applied to the HTI

296 membrane increases the majority of the shear stress in the straight channels to $(657\pm 63s^{-1})$. The
 297 Porifera membrane has the least consistent shear stress distribution on the membrane surface, with
 298 each spacer creating a shear 'dead-zone' along the length of the channel (Figure 5c). This
 299 inconsistency leads to 2 visually dominant shear distributions of 657 and $825\pm 63s^{-1}$ within the 0%
 300 channel. The Porifera module has the dense spacer of the three modules, and the low mechanical
 301 support creates a wider distribution and a much higher number of dead-zones. All three modules,
 302 however, overall demonstrate significant shear increases on the membrane surface with applied TMP
 303 pressure of 1.5bar.

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305 **Figure 6** Effect of TMP increase on shear strain at the (a) bulk fluid flow and (b) membrane surface.

306 Figure 6. shows the average values of the shear rate in the bulk average of the fluid, and
 307 represents the average perpendicular force exerted fluid in the draw-channel. The Porifera module
 308 is observed with the highest average shear rate in both the bulk fluid and at the membrane surface
 309 $(315$ and $526s^{-1})$, matching the observed trend on the membrane surface (Figure 5). The Toray has
 310 the lowest shear values, further matching the open nature of a larger channel. Overall, the three
 311 modules experience an increase of shear rate at both the bulk flow and membrane surface when TMP
 312 is applied. Additionally, the shear rate is much higher at the membrane surface, even with a relatively
 313 low CFV of $0.1m/s$ and narrow channel size (1-3mm across the modules). Additionally, on both the
 314 membrane and bulk fluid, an applied TMP of 1.5bar increases the shear by more than double for all
 315 the modules studies. This shear increase has implications on efficiency and CP performance, to be
 316 further investigated in this study.

317 *3.3 Reynolds number analysis of flow*

318 ANSYS Fluent was used to calculate the Reynolds number distribution on the membrane
 319 surface, as well as the membrane average and bulk average values to produce a detailed assessment
 320 of turbulence in the modules, under the effects of applied TMP (1.5bar). The assessment of Reynolds
 321 number in the draw-channel aims to provide a complimentary assessment to shear strain and further
 322 detail to an overall hydrodynamic analysis.

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326 **Figure 7.** Effect of TMP on Reynolds number on the membrane surface with the right and left
327 simulations 1 and 1.5bar TMP respectively for (a) Toray (b) HTI (c) Toray.

328 The Toray shows the lower Reynolds distribution (Figure 7a) of the SW modules, with the
329 straight channels of the membrane’s leaves showing a symmetrical and majority values of 56 ± 13 .
330 Symmetrical dead-zones of low turbulence are found in the corners of the membrane sleeves, as well
331 as a slight increase to 81 ± 13 on the corner of the glue-line, with an observed increase in the severity
332 of the glue-line turbulence between the 0% and 12% channels. An increase of Reynolds number to
333 69 ± 10 occurs under a TMP increase of 1.5bar, an explanation of which is the increase fluid velocity
334 due to a decrease in cross-sectional area (similar to Section 3.2). The HTI module has the most
335 extensive range in the distribution of Reynolds number across the membrane surface (Figure 7b).
336 Furthermore, the range across the outlet channel of the membrane leaf is of a much higher range than
337 the Toray module (10 vs 68 ± 10). This phenomenon can be explained by the less dense spacer of the
338 Toray draw module, and hence emphasises the importance of contour maps as a means of measuring
339 Reynolds distribution in FO modules with larger draw-channels (Section 3.1) [17].

340 In direct contrast to the shear data (Section 3.2), the Porifera module has the lowest average
341 Reynolds number at any TMP in the bulk fluid flow (Figure 9a). Additionally, at the membrane
342 surface, the Porifera module is observed as the lowest Reynolds number, and when TMP of 1.5bar is
343 applied (Figure 9b), also showing the least significant increase under applied pressure. Hence, the
344 Porifera module Reynolds number is the least sensitive to deformation, likely due to the low degree
345 of mechanical support offered by the draw-spacer and lack of turbulence promoters evenly
346 distributed like a SW mesh spacer. Additionally, the turbulence is much lower on the membrane
347 surface, an opposing trend to the shear strain data (Section 3.2). Overall, the detail shown in Figure 7
348 presents a similar contour profile to the shear strain data shown in Figure 5 but with less severity in
349 the effect of TMP (with the exception of the Porifera module). This detailed assessment of turbulence
350 through Reynolds number will be further characterised and linked to CP later in this study.
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353 **Figure. 9** Effect of TMP on Reynolds number in the (a) bulk fluid flow (b) membrane surface.

354 *3.4 TMP effects on CP*

355 The impact of TMP on deformation and subsequent draw channel contraction clearly affects the
356 hydrodynamics within FO modules, as such, an assessment of applying TMP on overall efficiency
357 and CP was made. The CP effects are then linked to the CFD hydrodynamic analysis from Sections
358 3.2-3.3 later in this study.

359 Firstly, the PF and SW flux data was assessed by expressing the flux as a percentage of the maximal
 360 possible flux to determine the overall flux efficiency (Equation 2) from experimental data previously
 361 reported in the literature [3, 17, 21]. The flux data was then used to determine osmotic efficiency,
 362 which characterizes the effectiveness of the osmotic component in the driving force (Equation 3).
 363 Subsequently, the flux data was processed in a CP modulus model [10] to characterise both ICP and
 364 ECP. The flux and osmotic efficiency is then compared against ICP and ECP across a range of TMPs,
 365 expressed as a percentage change from initial conditions to normalise different operating conditions.

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368 **Figure. 10** An assessment of efficiency and CP (ICP and ECP) for membranes out of a module and in
 369 a cross-flow cell (a) HTI (b) Porifera modules. Values are expressed as percentage changes from
 370 initial conditions at 0bar TMP, to normalize initial membrane conditions and characteristics.

371 The efficiency and CP analysis was first performed on the membrane scale, where data from the
 372 literature was used in this analysis was given at 0 and 4bar [3] (Figure 10). The data is expressed as a
 373 **percentagechange** from conditions at 0bar TMP (FO mode) to normalize the initial
 374 operating/membrane characteristics and allow for a direct comparison between membrane and
 375 module scale. Figure 10a is the HTI membrane and illustrates the overall trends we would expect for
 376 FO membranes operated with applied TMP. The overall efficiency increases by 13%, as we expect
 377 with the addition of hydraulic pressure in an FO process (whereby the hydraulic component of the
 378 driving force is almost 100% efficient). The osmotic component of the driving force decreases, as the
 379 higher pressure causes higher flux and thus the osmotic pressure is hindered by CP. This increase is
 380 illustrated in Figure 10a in both the ICP and ECP increase of 25 and 8% respectively, as expected with
 381 increasing flux [10]. The porifera membrane has a higher hydraulic permeability [3], and so higher
 382 flux with applied TMP thus the CP effects are greater with higher pressure/flux. The porifera
 383 membrane has a 46% increase in ICP, yet this is balanced with a higher overall flux efficiency increase
 384 as the effects of CP are balanced against the hydraulic permeability.
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The efficiency and CP analysis was then performed at the module scale, to determine the effects the different module and spacer designs exhibit under applied TMP, shown in Figure 11. The analysis was again performed on flux data from the literature, expressed as percentage changes from initial conditions at 0bar to allow for direct comparison.

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Figure. 11 An assessment of the change in efficiency and CP (ICP and ECP) with applied TMP for module scale (a) HTI (b) Toray (c) Porifera modules expressed as percentage changes from initial conditions at 0bar TMP.

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Figure 11a illustrates the efficiency and CP effects on a module scale for the HTI module, calculated based on flux data from the literature [17]. The TMP of 0-2.3bar is a narrower range than the membrane-scale shown in Figure 10a, but suits the purpose of analyzing efficiency and CP during membrane deformation and compares well to the overall picture given over a larger range of TMP's. The overall flux efficiency increase found by adding hydraulic pressure into the HTI SW module was over 20% from 0-2.3bar, matching the trends of the membrane-scale results. However, it is clearly seen that much of the efficiency gain is from 0-1bar of TMP, and lower subsequent increases (less than 2% improvement over the subsequent 1bar of applied TMP). Unexpectedly, the osmotic efficiency of the HTI module increases within the 1bar TMP range, in contrast to the trends predicted

408 from the membrane-scale analysis (Figure 10). The osmotic efficiency then decreases rapidly from 5%
409 to -8% over the next 1bar of TMP. An explanation for this phenomenon can be found by noting the
410 osmotic and overall efficiency trends matching with the deformation region of the HTI membrane
411 (Section 3.3). This unexpected trend indicates that the deformation has a positive effect on osmotic
412 and overall flux efficiency. With respect to CP analysis, the ICP increases proportionally with
413 increased TMP (and thus flux), as expected given the relatively constant nature of the S parameter in
414 FO membranes [10, 17]. In contrast to the ICP, ECP stays constant across the TMP's, and does not
415 increase as expected with higher TMP/flux. This stable ECP is in direct contrast the increasing ECP
416 effects under applied TMP in the membrane scale (Figure 10). An explanation for this is the changing
417 hydrodynamics in the draw channel, whereby TMP causes contraction, a narrower channel and a
418 faster CFV. This fast CFV and decreasing CFV mean that the changing hydrodynamics outweigh the
419 flux increase effects on ECP. Specifically the ECP is held constant by the higher Reynolds number,
420 and as such, higher 'k' value counterbalancing the increase usually expected by higher flux. The
421 Toray module demonstrates the same increase in overall efficiency within TMP's of 0-2.3bar,
422 however, with a much slower increase than the HTI at pressures of 0-1bar (Figure 11). This is coupled
423 with an osmotic efficiency that decreases, yet, the decrease slows at TMP's of 1-2bar of TMP,
424 indicating an optimum point of operation. As with the HTI, this optimum point matches with the
425 deformation region of the membrane, which is found at larger TMP's than the HTI due to less dense
426 spacer support (Section 3.1). ECP decreases only slightly with applied TMP, as with the HTI module.
427 The Porifera module (Figure 11c) has no CP data points illustrated, as the much higher deformation
428 and resultant channel occlusion was the primary factor for flux and this efficiency loss. This is
429 particularly apparent as the overall efficiency does not increase with applied TMP, in direct contrast
430 to the Toray and HTI modules. The efficiency data is also in direct contrast with the Porifera
431 membrane-scale data (Figure 10), indicating that occlusion is therefore not spread evenly and likely
432 contacting the spacer or wall to results in membrane area (and hence flux performance loss). Of note,
433 is the low TMP pressures recommended for Porifera operation [3], however, this indicates the
434 importance of mechanical support in the FO modules when PAO mode is used.

435 This first implication of this overall data is the importance of ECP when considering FO
436 membranes and modules, illustrating channel hydrodynamics impacting CP and improving CP
437 mitigation performance. The effect of membrane deformation on channel hydrodynamics is an
438 emerging idea previously reported in an empirical analysis of membrane deformation on CP, though
439 conducted at much higher pressures well past the where deformation no long increases significantly,
440 as the membrane likely already rests on the spacer support (2-14bar) [19]. However, the CP models
441 mentioned previously do not account for the deformation effects on flow profile. The next section of
442 this study will further assess this relation by linking the CFD hydrodynamic analysis to the
443 unexpected CP trends under applied pressure.

444 With the detailed assessment of the level of occlusion and hydrodynamic characterisation by
445 CFD (Sections 3.1-3.3), the analysis of the efficiency and CP (Section 3.4) can be compared and linked.
446 Current numerical CP models do not account for ECP based on irregular flow profiles caused by
447 deformation, and CFD analysis can provide a link to assess CP improvements by deformation. The
448 results are compared across the FO modules to assess the relationship between the CFD
449 characterisation of the draw channel flow profile, to link against experimental and CP analysis to
450 improve further the effectiveness and convenience of CFD in the future module and spacer design.

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453**Table 1.** A summary assessment of the effects of TMP on efficiency and CP of the three modules. In the draw, % calculated between 0 and 1.5 bar TMP

	HTI	Porifera	Toray
Reynolds (bulk)	25%	40%	20%
Reynolds (membrane)	10%	72%	10%
Shear strain (bulk)	34%	41%	33%
Shear strain (membrane)	33%	44%	35%
ICP	+21.9%	+n/a	+22.3%
ECP	0%	n/a	-2%
Overall Efficiency	+19.4%	+0.01%	+17.8%
Osmotic Efficiency	+1%	+0.01%	-22.2%
RSD	-7*%	-16*%	N/A

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*Data determined from experimental results previously reported [3].

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The CFD, efficiency and CP analysis are summarised in Table 1. The HTI module (under 1.5bar TMP) has an improved osmotic efficiency, in part due to the improved draw-channel hydrodynamics (Section 3.4). This is in direct correlation with the Shear and Reynolds number improvement in the module under 1.5bar TMP (Table 1). Given the high osmotic and overall efficiency performance of the HTI module, the bulk Reynolds number increase (5%) over the Toray can be concluded as the most important factor when considering the relatively similar shear strain values. However, this study does not include fouling effects whereby strain rate is more likely to be a major factor.

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The PF Porifera module however has the greatest Reynolds increase (41% in the bulk flow), due to the high degree of occlusion (Section 3.1) and high turbulence from the uneven flow profile (Section 3.3). However, the relationship between turbulence and efficiency is balanced against the membrane-area loss for the Porifera module, indicating that mechanical support must be balanced against flow improvements overall. The HTI and Toray modules experienced lower increases in turbulence (Table 1), but due to the higher mechanical support maintained a high membrane area availability. The shear strain rate (Table 1) improves by approx. 40% across all modules, is also strongly linked to increased flux performance, with shear strain on the membrane surface likely to disrupt the ECP boundary layer on the draw-channel and explain the higher-than-expected osmotic efficiency. The significant increases in Reynolds number and shear strain (Table 1) seem to link more directly to osmotic efficiency in the deformation region of the membrane when the flow profile is the most irregular. As such, future spacer design should seek to improve shear strain for –increased flux, and Reynolds number should RSD improvement be an aim but recognise the less direct link than the mass transfer coefficient ‘k’ (Equation 7) from CP models would suggest. This indicates that ECP in the draw-channel plays a greater role in the draw-side than initially assumed [9-11]. Furthermore, models that account for ECP in the draw-channel should further aim to take into account irregular channel shape with the assistance of CFD to determine a draw-channel flow profile. Overall, most notably, it can be seen that over CP effects decrease within the deformation range of the membrane modules. With 1.5bar across all modules, the effects of CP are lower; as such, this region is likely the most efficient operating point of the FO modules when in FO and PAO modes.

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4. Conclusions

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By comparing pressure loss data, the levels of occlusion at 1.5bar of TMP were found as 16%, 49% and 12% between the Toray, Porifera and Toray modules respectively. The difference in occlusion between the modules was explained by observing the degree of mechanical support that the draw-spacers offered. Shear strain contour maps from CFD demonstrated a consistent increase in shear strain across all three modules, with an average increase of 62% at the membrane surface under 1.5bar TMP (HTI experienced the most significant increase from $(230 \pm 33s^{-1})$ to $(663 \pm 33s^{-1})$). Reynolds number demonstrated a consistent increase across the modules, with an average increase of 31% in

491 the draw-channel across the modules under 1.5bar TMP. Reynolds number was highest in the
492 channel, in contrast to shear values. An assessment of efficiency and CP showed overall efficiency
493 increased in the SW modules, but not the PF due to a high degree of occlusion likely detracting from
494 the membrane area. However, osmotic efficiency did not decrease consistently as expected and
495 deformation was found to positively increase osmotic efficiency indicating that the optimum
496 operating pressure for FO (PAO) lies when the membrane is deforming into the draw-channel.
497 Additionally, hydrodynamics obtained from CFD assessment such as Reynolds number were
498 incorporated into the ECP model to improve accuracy over simpler calculations used currently.
499 Reynolds number increases in the bulk fluid were found to be modest and not strongly related to flux
500 performance of ECP decreases. However, shear strain at the membrane surface was found the most
501 important factor when predicting flux performance. The implications for this extend to the further
502 improvement of draw-spacer design, where the lessons learned can mean predictions can be made
503 from CFD and assessed before costly and time-consuming experimental testing.
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